

Physicochemical Characteristics of Hydroxide Hydrogels of some Transition Metals

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WHITING and Turner¹ found that the rate of decomposition of the hydrogels was influenced by the grain size and surface area of the dispersed phase. The effect of vapour pressure on decomposition has also been investigated by a number of authors²⁻⁴ Chalyi *et al.*⁵ and Ermolenko *et al.*⁶ have studied the thermal decomposition of several metal hydroxides with the help of DTA and TGA.

Experimental

All the six hydroxide hydrogels of the transition metal ions were synthesised following the wet interaction process of the respective salts at 5% concentration (w/v) in alkaline medium at pH 8 with ammonium hydroxide. Salts taken were $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{MnCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ —all of G.R./AnalaR grade. Each hydrogel was synthesised at a time and under more or less identical experimental condition to have uniform textural characteristics. In case of manganese hydroxide hydrogel, about 2.5 g dm^{-3} of ascorbic acid was added to prevent the oxidation of Mn^{II} before addition of NH_4OH . The formed hydrogel was vacuum-dried and stored in air-tight condition to inhibit further aerial oxidation.

Results and Discussion

Chemical analysis of all the hydrogels was performed which revealed that the content of impurities was almost negligible. In case of manganese hydroxide hydrogel, it was found to contain 4.55% $\text{Mn}(\text{OH})_2$ in spite of taking all the precautions which resulted in its slight brownish colour. Some of the physicochemical characteristics of the synthesised hydroxide hydrogels are given in the Table 1.

An examination of Table 1 reveals that the synthesised hydroxide hydrogels differed to a considerable extent which might be due to the nature of the cation, as the orientation of water either as OH or as H_2O in the primary and secondary coordination sphere is solely dependant on it.

The hardness of the hydrogel, which is related to the bond strength as well as aggregate nature, was examined empirically by hand-feel method. No correlation could be made between the ionic radius and the hardness of the hydrogels.

TABLE 1—PHYSICOCHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF SYNTHETIC HYDROXIDE HYDROGELS

Sl. no.	Hydrogel	Colour appearance	Total water content %	Bulk density g cm^{-3}
1	Chromium hydroxide	Greyish green, hard	38.5	0.414
2	Manganese hydroxide	Light brown, semi-hard	19.9	0.366
3	Cobalt hydroxide	Deep pink, soft	13.7	0.393
4	Nickel hydroxide	Apple green semi-hard	22.9	0.447
5	Copper hydroxide	Light blue, soft	31.9	0.448
6	Zinc hydroxide	White, hard	22.3	0.279

The total water content was determined by heat-treating the samples at 700° for 2 h. The sequence of the cations in the hydroxide lattice with respect to the total water content may be represented as $\text{Cr}^{\text{III}} > \text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} > \text{Zn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Mn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$. The water content of the hydroxide hydrogel was found to follow an inverse relationship with the ionic radius of the respective cations as shown in Fig. 1a, which may be explained through the theory of cation hydration.

Fig. 1 Relationship between (a) total water content and ionic radius, and (b) 1st endothermic peak (DTA) and ionic radius of synthetic hydroxide hydrogels of some transition metal cations. (O) Cr^{III} , (Δ) Mn^{II} , ($\square$) Co^{II} , (+) Ni^{II} , (x) Cu^{II} , and ($\bullet$) Zn^{II} .

The bulk density results indicated that the synthesised hydrogels possessed highly open porous

structure and as such the internal surface area was of significant order. The bulk density result could not be correlated to either the atomic weight of the cations or the experimentally found water content. Thus it appears that the bulk density is a textural property of the hydrogel which is controlled by the growth of gel network during formation.

The hydrogels are formed in the aqueous phase possessing an oriented structure with complete engulfment of the dispersion phase. But on subsequent ageing and drying the material may or may not attain a periodicity in long range order. For this purpose, X-ray analysis was performed with all the dried hydrogels for getting a qualitative idea about the crystallinity of the material. The hydroxides of chromium, manganese and cobalt were found to be amorphous. But the hydroxides of nickel, copper and zinc were found to possess crystalline structure showing definite diffraction pattern. The X-ray diffraction results are shown in the Table 2

TABLE 2—X-RAY DIFFRACTION RESULTS OF HYDROXIDE HYDROGELS

Nickel hydroxide hydrogel		Copper hydroxide hydrogel		Zinc hydroxide hydrogel	
d (Å)	I	d (Å)	I	d (Å)	I
9.0	w	7.9	vw	17.0	w
4.62	vs	6.5	ms	11.0	w
4.05	w	5.4	ms	8.5	w
2.72	s	5.2	vw	8.0	w
2.55	vw	5.0	vw	7.4	w
2.34	vs	4.8	vw	6.2	vw
1.76	ms	3.96	ms	5.5	vw
1.565	s	3.2	ms	4.42	w
1.489	ms	2.95	w	4.2	ms
1.36	w	2.80	w	3.8	w
1.34	w	2.70	ms	3.54	w
1.305	w	2.62	vw	3.4	w
		2.54	vs	3.15	w
		2.48	w	2.74	vs
		2.44	w	2.60	w
		2.38	vw	2.55	w
		2.30	vw	2.50	vw
		2.15	w	2.40	w
		2.10	w	2.34	vw
		2.08	vw	2.16	w
		1.97	vw	2.0	vw
		1.92	vw	1.83	vw
		1.88	vw	1.75	vw
		1.83	w	1.62	vw
		1.75	ms	1.575	s
		1.72	vw	1.55	w
		1.68	vw	1.49	vw
		1.64	vw	1.365	w
		1.60	w	1.345	w
		1.57	w	1.336	vw
		1.542	w	1.275	vw
		1.51	w		
		1.47	vw		
		1.44	w		
		1.415	vw		
		1.35	vw		
		1.32	w		
		1.29	vw		

w=weak, m=medium, s=strong.

whereas others did not. There are references⁷ of crystalline character for both manganese and cobalt hydroxides. Thus it appears that by varying the experimental conditions, hydrogels of these types of cations may be synthesised either in crystalline or in amorphous form. In order to analyse the different types of water associated with the hydrogels of the transition metal cations, differential thermal analysis was performed, with the powder material. The DTA curves are shown upto 1000° in Fig. 2. All the hydrogels exhibited 3 to 4 endothermic peaks in this temperature region which were

Fig. 2. DTA curves of synthetic hydroxide hydrogels.

associated with the expulsion of water from the hydrogel structure. This shows that the bonding of water in the hydrogel lattice was heterogeneous in nature. The first endothermic peak was found to follow an inverse relationship with the cationic radius of the divalent cations (Fig. 1b). The exothermic peaks were mainly associated with some disorder-order transformation of the partially dehydrated hydrogels.

Conclusion : Although the processing conditions of the hydroxide hydrogels of transition metals were kept more or less same in order to have uniform texture, yet there were significant differences in the physicochemical characteristics. Some were crystalline and some amorphous. The bulk density and hardness could not be correlated with either the

Under the present experimental condition, some of the hydrogels attained the crystalline structure

ionic radius or the atomic weight of the elements. But the total water content and the first endothermic peak temperature (DTA) were found to follow an inverse relationship with the ionic radius of the respective cations.

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Syntheses of Hydroxytriazenes

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BAMBERGER¹, Gebhard and Thompson² were the first to synthesis hydroxytriazenes. The complexing ability of these compounds has been

examined by Elkins and Hunter³. The analytical uses of these compounds have been evaluated for the first time by Sogani and Bhattacharya⁴. Sogani *et al.*⁵⁻¹⁰ prepared a large number of these compounds and explored their utilities in analytical chemistry. Taking into consideration the increasing importance of hydroxytriazenes as chelating agents in analytical chemistry, ten new hydroxytriazenes have been synthesised.

Experimental

Synthesis of ligands: Isopropylhydroxylamine solution was prepared by reducing isonitropropane (25.0 ml) with zinc dust (30.0 g) in presence of NH₄Cl (30.0 g) at 0–15°. It was coupled at 0±2° with benzene diazonium chloride prepared from aniline (18.6 g). Sodium acetate solution (30%) was added occasionally. The granular yellow product was filtered off and crystallised twice from ethanol—water mixture to give light yellow crystals of 3-hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-phenyltriazene (9.0g). Other ligands were prepared similarly by coupling isopropylhydroxylamine with the corresponding substituted benzene diazonium chloride. Elemental analysis and physical characteristics of the ligands thus prepared are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Sl. no.	Compd.	Mol. formula	M.p. ^a °C	Colour	Analy-is : Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
1.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-phenyltriazene	C ₉ H ₁₃ N ₃ O	111 ^a	Light yellow	60.19 (60.34)	7.37 (7.26)	22.69 (23.46)
2.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-p-tolytriazene	C ₁₀ H ₁₅ N ₃ O	133 ^a	Light violet	61.80 (62.17)	7.84 (7.77)	21.50 (21.76)
3.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl 1-p-chlorophenyltriazene	C ₉ H ₁₁ N ₃ OCl	191 ^a	Violet	51.04 (50.58)	6.00 (5.62)	19.65 (19.67)
4.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-p-bromophenyltriazene	C ₉ H ₁₁ N ₃ OBr	114 ^b	Light yellow	41.29 (41.86)	4.68 (4.65)	16.63 (16.27)
5.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-p-methoxyphenyltriazene	C ₁₀ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂	110 ^b	Light brown	57.61 (57.41)	7.38 (7.17)	20.24 (20.09)
6.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-p-carboxyphenyltriazene	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₃	180 ^a	Light cream	53.66 (53.81)	6.03 (5.82)	18.6 (18.83)
7.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-m-acetylphenyltriazene	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂	118 ^b	Light brown	59.89 (59.72)	6.88 (6.78)	18.46 (19.00)
8.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-p-nitrophenyltriazene	C ₉ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₃	125 ^b	Shining dark brown	48.82 (48.21)	5.42 (5.35)	24.82 (25.00)
9.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-m-nitrophenyltriazene	C ₉ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₃	157 ^a	Shining light yellow	48.82 (48.21)	5.42 (5.35)	24.82 (25.00)
10.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-o-nitrophenyltriazene	C ₉ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₃	82 ^b	Golden yellow	48.82 (48.21)	5.42 (5.35)	24.82 (25.00)

* Crystallised from : ^a ethanol-water, ^b ethanol.